

Socio-Economic and Environmental Impacts of Urban Residential Power Outages: A Case Study of Federal Capital City Phase 1, Abuja, Nigeria

MUSA, Unekwuwojo Godswill; AREMU, James Kayode, & SHUAIBU, Isah

Department of Geography, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria godswillmusa@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study assesses the socio-economic and environmental impacts of power outages on residential users in Federal Capital City (FCC) Phase 1, Abuja, Nigeria, through the lens of Protection Motivation Theory (PMT). The research examines how power outages are affecting residents' livelihood activities socio-economically and environmentally. Using a systematic random sampling technique, data were collected from 400 households and analyzed with the Relative Importance Index (RII). Findings revealed that power outages significantly disrupt residents' socio-economic and environmental well-being. Noise pollution from electricity power generating sets' emerged as the most critical environmental effect (RII = 0.726), causing stress, disrupting sleep, and posing security risks. Expenditure on alternative power sources was the most significant socio-economic burden (RII = 0.691), increasing financial strain and threatening household economic stability. These challenges trigger threat appraisal in PMT, as residents perceive the severity of disruptions to health, comfort, and economic stability. Unlike previous studies focusing on commercial impacts of power outages, this research highlights the livelihood and health implications for urban residential households, contributing to knowledge on energy poverty in Nigeria's capital. The study recommends adopting reliable and sustainable energy solutions, particularly solar energy, to mitigate these adverse effects.

Keywords: energy poverty, socio-economic impact, environmental effects, Protection Motivation Theory, power outage. Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Urbanisation has sharply increased the demand for reliable and sustainable energy, yet power outages persist as a major impediment to socio-economic development across many sectors globally (Vo et al., 2024; Avordeh et al., 2024). These interruptions disrupt daily livelihoods, exacerbate energy poverty, and drive environmental degradation through heightened reliance on fossil fuel-based backup systems, such as electric power generating sets (Rateau & Choplin, 2022). In Nigeria, where erratic electricity supply costs the economy an estimated US\$25 billion (World Bank, 2021), understanding the impacts on urban households is critical for advancing sustainable energy solutions. This paper examines the socio-economic and environmental effects of power outages in Federal Capital City (FCC) Phase 1, Abuja, applying Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) to explore residents' threat appraisals and adaptive responses, such as solar energy adoption.

Global electricity demand rose by 4.0% in 2024, driven by heatwave-related cooling needs (208 TWh). This led to a 1.4% increase in fossil generation and a 1.6% rise in power sector emissions to 14.6 billion tonnes of CO₂, as clean energy growth could not fully meet demand (Graham & Fulghum, 2025). Sub-Saharan Africa faces acute power outages challenges, with 600 million people lacking electricity access in 2022, reducing business productivity and deepening poverty (International Energy Agency [IEA], 2023). Nigeria has an energy shortfall of 5,398 MW for over 200 million people in 2025 (Lot et al., 2025). In Nigeria, approximately 94% of grid-connected households face reliability issues, with 69.8% experiencing 4–14 power outages per week lasting over two hours, and 97% receiving less than 23 hours of daily electricity supply, driving reliance on polluting backups such as electric power generating sets (Luzi et al., 2020). Audu and Sule (2025) contend that rapid urban expansion in Abuja has intensified energy demand, with outages causing financial strain, noise pollution, and health risks from diesel powered generator emissions.

The research problem addressed by this study stems from the persistent unreliability of the national grid, which perpetuates energy insecurity among residential users in FCC Phase 1. Despite extensive analysis of outages in industrial and commercial contexts (Ogunlami et al., 2021; Chinedu et al., 2025), residential-specific insights on alternative power sources and pollution remain limited. The aim is to analyse the socio-economic and environmental effects of power outages on residential users in FCC Phase 1, Abuja. The objective is to assess these effects using data from households surveyed in 2023, highlighting how perceived threats drive sustainable adaptations. The scope covers residential neighbourhoods in FCC Phase 1, excluding administrative zones.

This study aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 7, promoting affordable and clean energy, and Nigeria's commitment to a 47% reduction in carbon emissions (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2025). By illuminating residential impacts, it informs policies for resilient energy infrastructure, fostering equitable access and environmental sustainability globally.

CONCEPTUAL ANCHOR AND RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

Power Outage

Power outages refer to the temporary loss of electrical power supply, disrupting essential services and household activities (Ayodele-Olajire et al., 2023). This study adopts the concept to analyze how outages affect residents' livelihoods, focusing on their economic and environmental impacts in urban residential settings.

Renewable Energy

Renewable energy encompasses energy sources derived from naturally replenishing resources but flow-limited, such as solar, wind, and geothermal (U.S. Energy Information Administration [EIA], 2024). It offers a sustainable alternative to unreliable grid power in Nigeria, reducing energy poverty and environmental degradation (Idoko et al., 2024). This study adopts renewable energy to explore its potential to mitigate outage-related disruptions, emphasizing its role in promoting economic stability and environmental health in FCC Phase 1.

Theoretical Framework

Protection Motivation Theory (PMT)

Developed by Rogers in 1975 and refined by Maddux and Rogers (1983), Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) explains how individuals respond to perceived threats through protective behaviors. PMT comprises two processes: threat appraisal, assessing the severity and vulnerability of a threat, and coping appraisal, evaluating the efficacy and feasibility of a response. In this study, PMT frames residents' responses to power outages, where the severity of socio-economic (e.g., financial strain) and environmental (e.g., noise pollution) impacts triggers threat appraisal, and solar energy's reliability and affordability drive coping appraisal, encouraging adoption (Ezzati et al., 2025). PMT is relevant as it links outage-induced challenges to residents' motivation to adopt sustainable energy solutions in FCC Phase 1.

Empirical Review

Globally, power outages pose significant challenges to sustainable development, impacting socio-economic activities and environmental health. In Pakistan, Ali et al. (2024) surveyed 349 community members across diverse regions, using a 22-factor questionnaire. They found that outages reduced manufacturing output, leisure, public administration efficiency, and educational opportunities, while increasing reliance on traditional energy sources. The study recommends timely energy project completion to meet community needs and enhance sustainability.

In Africa, studies highlight the severe impacts of power outages on businesses and households, compounded by limited infrastructure. In Accra, Ghana, Nduhuura et al. (2021) surveyed 496 urban households, employing correlation and regression analyses. They reported that outages disrupted safety, food access, social services, and caused appliance damage, with low income and large household size linked to higher impact severity. The study advocates for improved electricity reliability to support sustainable development. In Collins Chabane Local Municipality, South Africa, Mabunda et al. (2023) used a mixed-methods approach with 100 questionnaires and 25 interviews to assess loadshedding impacts on SMEs. Results showed a 61% revenue loss and 59% employee layoffs, with no demographic influence on impact severity. They recommend government subsidies for solar panels to mitigate economic losses. In Zambia, Ahmed et al. (2023) surveyed 54 households, using Bayesian inference. They found outages caused food spoilage, reduced work capacity, limited cooking options, and self-reported depression in 21% of respondents, with sleep disruptions as a significant predictor. The study suggests reliable electricity to reduce mental health impacts.

In Nigeria, power outages significantly affect both businesses and households, with reliance on electric power generating sets exacerbating socio-economic and environmental challenges. In Gwagwalada, Adekanbi (2024) investigated outage impacts on small businesses, though methodology details were limited. Frequent outages increased operational costs and reduced profitability due to reliance on electric power generating sets, which also caused environmental degradation. The study recommends reforms to enhance power reliability. In Kogi State, Abaukaka (2023) surveyed businesses and households, using inferential statistics. Unstable electricity increased business overhead costs, contributing to inflation, and led households to use unsafe fuels like firewood, posing health and environmental risks. The study recommends solar and wind energy solutions. In the Federal Capital Territory, Yelwa and Awe (2018) used a survey and logit model to analyze outage impacts on SMEs. Outages reduced productivity due to costly electric power generating sets, with small-scale operators most affected. They recommend institutional reforms for reliable power supply. In Uyo, Michael and Ekong (2018) surveyed 50 urban households using descriptive analysis. Households spent 5–15% of income on electric power generating sets and firewood, causing health and environmental risks. They recommend household ownership of electricity infrastructure to reduce vandalism.

While these studies provide critical insights into the impacts of power outages, gaps remain in understanding their effects on urban residential households in FCC Phase 1, Abuja. Existing research focuses on SMEs (Adekanbi, 2024; Yelwa & Awe, 2018; Mabunda et al., 2023), mixed populations (Abaukaka, 2023), or broader household/community contexts (Nduhuura et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2023; Michael & Ekong, 2018; Ali et al., 2024). Specific wards, such as Garki, Wuse, and Maitama in FCC Phase 1, with diverse socio-economic profiles, remain underexplored in terms of residential-specific socio-economic impacts (e.g., expenditure on alternatives) and environmental effects (e.g., noise pollution from electric power generating sets). This study addresses these gaps, contributing to knowledge on energy poverty in Nigeria's capital.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study area is Federal Capital City (FCC) Phase 1, located in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria (Latitude 9° 0' to 9° 8' N, Longitude 7° 27' to 7° 32' E). FCC Phase 1 comprises five districts: Garki, Wuse, Maitama, Asokoro, and Central Area, covering approximately 58 km² with an elevation of 631 m above sea level (Figures 1 &

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2) The projected population in 2023 is 544,409, with an average household size of 4.7, yielding 115,832 households (National Population Commission, 2019). Excluding the administrative Central Area, the effective population is 99,594 households across residential districts (Musa et al., 2016). The area features a tropical climate with a rainy season (April–October, 1000–1500 mm rainfall) and dry season (November–March, temperatures 19°C to 34°C), influencing solar energy potential (Nigerian Meteorological Agency, 2025; Weatherspark, 2023).

Figure 1: Federal Capital City Phase 1, in FCT, Location
 Source: Abuja Geographical Information System (AGIS) (2008)

Figure 2: Federal Capital City Phase 1, FCT
 Source: Abuja Geographical Information System (AGIS) (2008)

Methods

This study employs a descriptive research design to assess the socio-economic and environmental effects of power outages on urban residential households in Federal Capital City (FCC) Phase 1, Abuja, Nigeria. The design focuses on survey methods to evaluate residents' perceptions of outage impacts. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to households in FCC Phase 1, targeting variables such as food spoilage, communication disruption, appliance damage, sleeping discomfort, water interruption, lateness to work, expenditure on alternatives, air pollution from electric power generating sets, and noise pollution from electric power generating sets. Multistage

sampling was used: stratified sampling delineated districts (Garki, Wuse, Maitama, Asokoro), while random sampling selected households.

The sample size was calculated using Yamane's (1967) formula, yielding 400 questionnaires, with 330 (82.5%) retrieved for analysis. Data were ranked on a 5-point Likert scale (Extremely Insignificant = 1 to Extremely Significant = 5) and analyzed using the Relative Importance Index (RII) to rank effects, computed as

Relative Importance Index (RII) is given by the formula:

$$RII = \frac{5n_5 + 4n_4 + 3n_3 + 2n_2 + 1n_1}{A * N}$$

Where, according to Johnson and Lebreton (2004):

n_5 = Number of respondents for extremely significant

n_4 = Number of respondents for significant

n_3 = Number of respondents for slightly significant

n_2 = Number of respondents for insignificant

n_1 = Number of respondents for extremely insignificant

A (Highest Weight) = 5, and N (Total number of respondents) = 330.

Analysis was conducted via SPSS version 25. Ethical considerations included informed consent and confidentiality. Results were presented textually and tabular.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Economic and Environmental Effects of Power Outage in FCC Phase 1

This subsection discusses the objective to analyse the socio-economic effects of the urban darkness period in FCC Phase 1, Abuja. Data collected for each socio-economic variable were ranked on a five-point scale: Extremely Insignificant (EI) = 1, Insignificant (I) = 2, Slightly Significant (SS) = 3, Significant (S) = 4, and Extremely Significant (ES) = 5. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The Socio-Economic Effects of Urban Darkness Period in the Study Area

Variables	EI	I	SS	S	ES	Total
Food Spoilage	71	50	69	19	121	330
Communication/Entertainment disruption	31	89	59	60	91	330
Damage to electrical appliances	81	100	58	10	81	330
Sleeping Discomfort	30	71	68	60	101	330
Water supply Interruption	50	60	49	71	100	330
Air Pollution from Generators	50	61	39	70	110	330
Noise Pollution from Generators	60	41	19	51	159	330
Lateness to Work	110	50	59	81	30	330
Expenditure on other Alternatives	61	49	19	81	120	330

Source: Field Survey (2023).

Table 1 displays the frequency distribution of respondents' perceptions of power outage impacts. Noise pollution from electric power generating sets was rated highest, with 159 respondents considering it extremely significant. The persistent noise, especially at night, disrupts sleep, causes stress, and poses security risks as distress calls at night may go unheard. Food spoilage came next, with 121 respondents rating it extremely significant, as outages compromise refrigeration, leading to financial losses and health risks from spoiled food. In contrast, lateness to work was considered least significant, with 110 respondents rating it extremely insignificant. This suggests that most residents have adapted to the challenges of power outages and have found ways to mitigate their impact on their work schedules such as preparing or ironing their clothes in bulk prior to getting ready to go to work. These findings are consistent with studies in Ghana by Nduhuura et al. (2021) and in Zambia by Ahmed et al. (2023), which identified sleep disruption and food insecurity as major impacts of power outages.

Relative Importance Index (RII) Analysis of Socio-Economic Effects

To further assess the significance of the socio-economic effects, the Relative Importance Index (RII) formula was applied. This analysis ranks the variables based on their weighted importance from the survey data, shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Relative Importance Index (RII) of the Socio-Economic Effects of Urban Darkness Period in FCC Phase 1

Variables	Total Response	N	A*N	RII	Rank
Noise Pollution from Generators	1198	330	1650	0.726	1
Expenditure on Other Alternatives	1140	330	1650	0.691	2
Sleeping Discomfort	1121	330	1650	0.679	3
Air Pollution from Generators	1119	330	1650	0.678	4
Water Supply Interruption	1101	330	1650	0.667	5
Communication/Entertainment Disruption	1081	330	1650	0.655	6
Food Spoilage	1059	330	1650	0.642	7
Damage to Electrical Appliances	900	330	1650	0.545	8
Lateness to Work	861	330	1650	0.522	9

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Note: A (Highest Weight) = 5; N = 330

The results from Table 2 presented the Relative Importance Index (RII), which provides a more robust measure of the significance of each variable. Noise pollution from generators again emerged as the most critical impact (RII = 0.726), followed by expenditure on alternative energy sources (RII = 0.691) and sleeping discomfort (RII = 0.679). This confirms that environmental and financial burdens are at the forefront of residents' experiences during outages. Conversely, lateness to work had the lowest RII (0.522), followed by appliance damage (0.545).

The ranking demonstrates that residents are more concerned with effects that directly affect daily well-being (noise, discomfort) and financial security (high spending on alternatives) than with productivity losses such as lateness. These findings resonate with studies in Ghana (Nduhuura et al., 2021) and Nigeria (Michael & Ekong, 2018), which reported that urban households spend between 5–15% of income on generator fuel and experience health and lifestyle disruptions as more severe than workplace productivity losses.

Theoretical and Policy Implications

The results align with Protection Motivation Theory, where power outages trigger threat appraisal, with residents perceiving noise pollution, air pollution from electric power generating sets, food spoilage, and expenditure on alternatives as severe, recurring threats to health, finances, and comfort. Frequent outages and unreliable grid supply heighten vulnerability, consistent with findings in Nigeria (Abaukaka, 2023) and Ghana (Nduhuura et al., 2021). These findings underscore the need for urban energy policies in FCC Phase 1, such as subsidies for solar PV systems and noise regulations for electric power generating sets, to reduce environmental and financial burdens caused by expenditure on fuel for generators. Such measures support Sustainable Development Goal 7 for affordable, clean energy (UNDP, 2025).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that power outages in Federal Capital City (FCC) Phase 1, Abuja, create serious socio-economic and environmental challenges. Noise pollution from generators was identified as the most critical environmental effect, while expenditure on alternative energy sources emerged as the leading socio-economic burden. These findings highlight the need for sustainable solutions to reduce household vulnerabilities and advance Nigeria's clean energy goals under SDG 7.

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Federal Ministry of Power, in partnership with private energy providers, should prioritise investment in renewable energy infrastructure, particularly solar photovoltaic systems, through subsidies and incentives to reduce reliance on polluting generators.
- ii. The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and the Federal Capital Territory Administration (FCTA) should enforce stricter regulations on generator noise and emissions, while promoting the adoption of quieter and cleaner alternatives.
- iii. Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), community groups, and NGOs should collaborate on public awareness campaigns that highlight the health, economic, and environmental risks of prolonged generator use while educating households on affordable renewable energy options.
- iv. Urban planners and policymakers should integrate reliable energy supply into Abuja's development strategy, ensuring that residential districts like FCC Phase 1 are prioritised for stable electricity provision to enhance household well-being and economic productivity.

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